

Table S1 Mean net economic results for the 80 "with" sensor scenarios (5th and 95th percentiles shown in parenthesis).

Scenario	Sensor performance^a	Alert notification interval (days)	€ '000
1	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	1	274.5 (264.42; 284.58)
1	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	7	277.95 (267.5; 286.92)
1	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	14	277.93 (268.09; 286.8)
1	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	30	277.81 (267.98; 287.19)
1	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	1	273.33 (263.32; 283.29)
1	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	7	277.5 (267.37; 287.28)
1	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	14	278.26 (269.09; 287.71)
1	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	30	278.3 (269.09; 287.52)
1	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	1	272.98 (262.75; 282.26)
1	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	7	277.78 (268.09; 287.15)
1	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	14	277.82 (268.12; 287.15)
1	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	30	278.27 (269.31; 287.56)
1	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	1	273.84 (263.25; 283.78)
1	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	7	277.75 (267.94; 287.17)
1	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	14	278.61 (269.32; 287.82)
1	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	30	278.35 (268.3; 287.74)
2	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	1	278.83 (270.35; 287.69)
2	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	7	280.42 (270.99; 289.48)
2	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	14	279.68 (271.48; 288.27)
2	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	30	277.37 (268.85; 286.99)
2	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	1	276.88 (267.79; 286.21)
2	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	7	280.94 (272.08; 291.05)
2	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	14	279.98 (270.92; 289.47)
2	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	30	278.86 (269.06; 287.93)
2	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	1	277.4 (267.54; 286.58)
2	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	7	280.93 (271.28; 290.82)
2	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	14	280.59 (270.52; 289.52)
2	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	30	278.84 (269.48; 288.76)
2	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	1	279.4 (270.26; 289.26)
2	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	7	281.26 (272.12; 290.46)
2	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	14	280.6 (271.42; 289.78)
2	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	30	279.45 (269.63; 288.6)
3	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	1	282.79 (273.08; 292.22)
3	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	7	284.01 (274.64; 293.1)
3	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	14	283.04 (273.59; 292.92)
3	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	30	280.5 (271.01; 290.56)
3	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	1	280.64 (272.09; 289.48)
3	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	7	284.28 (274.81; 293.61)
3	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	14	283.75 (273.12; 293.86)
3	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	30	281.44 (271.66; 291.21)
3	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	1	281.43 (273.08; 290.44)
3	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	7	284.54 (275.12; 294.03)
3	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	14	283.81 (274.74; 292.43)
3	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	30	282.65 (273.29; 291.69)
3	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	1	283.24 (273.06; 292.18)
3	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	7	285.14 (276.07; 294.28)
3	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	14	284.49 (275.2; 292.83)

3	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	30	282.86 (273.33; 292.74)
4	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	1	270.18 (260.49; 279.21)
4	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	7	277.3 (267.97; 286.39)
4	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	14	276.72 (267; 285.46)
4	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	30	273.38 (263.45; 283.43)
4	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	1	268.21 (257.96; 277.77)
4	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	7	276.76 (267.43; 285.55)
4	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	14	275.67 (265.68; 285.88)
4	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	30	273.72 (263.07; 283.16)
4	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	1	269.26 (259.51; 278.8)
4	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	7	276.98 (266.99; 287.16)
4	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	14	276.71 (266.17; 286.53)
4	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	30	274.65 (264.59; 285.36)
4	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	1	277.43 (268.37; 285.86)
4	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	7	278.51 (268.45; 287.62)
4	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	14	277.11 (267.64; 287.05)
4	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	30	274.64 (264.27; 284.17)
5	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	1	275.31 (266.01; 284.68)
5	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	7	284.46 (275.93; 294.27)
5	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	14	284 (274.23; 293.32)
5	Se: 68% Sp: 88%	30	280.4 (271.19; 289.57)
5	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	1	273.7 (264.31; 282.82)
5	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	7	283.43 (274.48; 292.46)
5	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	14	283.43 (274.87; 292.86)
5	Se: 75% Sp: 79%	30	280.85 (271.1; 290.24)
5	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	1	274.46 (264.7; 283.78)
5	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	7	283.66 (274.44; 292.62)
5	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	14	283.84 (274.36; 293.11)
5	Se: 82% Sp: 81%	30	281.7 (271.99; 290.82)
5	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	1	282.56 (273; 291.73)
5	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	7	285.57 (276.45; 293.64)
5	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	14	284.74 (276.4; 293.28)
5	Se: 88% Sp: 91%	30	282.04 (273.35; 291.12)

^a Se = Sensitivity; Sp = Specificity

